

Wwise Demo for WAC2022

Philippe Milot
Audiokinetic inc.
pmilot@audiokinetic.com

OVERVIEW

Audiokinetic inc. will present a working build of a web-based game integrating the Wwise SDK to generate all game audio in real time. Wwise is a complete cross-platform solution for interactive audio, and functional support for web browsers and Web Audio will be presented publicly for the first time at the conference.

The main goal of the presentation is to show how the Wwise development tools work in the context of a game running on a web browser, and present the similarities and differences compared to working with other gaming platforms. At the same time, Audiokinetic inc. will share its experience integrating the Wwise SDK with the Emscripten compiler toolchain and explain potential roadblocks that other integrators may run into.

1. DEMO OUTLINE

1.1 Introduction (5 mins)

A brief explanation of Audiokinetic and the Wwise product, the markets in which Wwise is often used, and why the web is now considered a relevant platform for these markets. We will also briefly review our previous prototype work from 2019 which was originally presented at the W3C Workshop on Web Games in Seattle.

1.2 Game demo

A first live run of the game will be presented in full screen in both Google Chrome and Firefox. Various sections will showcase different features of the Wwise sound engine, such as real-time synthesis, Interactive Music, and Spatial Audio.

1.3 Technical overview

A technical overview of the previous demo will be presented in the form of slides with diagrams explaining the relationship between the Wwise SDK, the game engine, the Emscripten toolchain, the Web browser environment, and the Web server.

1.4 Tools demo

The game will be shown again, this time with two side-by-side windows: the Wwise Profiler on the left, and the game running in Google Chrome on the right. We will demonstrate how the Wwise Profiler can be used to display live data about the real-time audio rendering happening in the browser. Then, we will show how the audio itself can be controlled and changed by the Wwise Authoring tool while the game is running by muting/soloing sound sources, changing volumes, bypassing effects, etc.

1.5 Profiler technical overview

A technical overview of the previous Wwise Profiler demo will be presented in the form of slides with diagrams explaining the relationship between the Wwise runtime, Wwise Authoring application, and the web server. The connection and communication flow of the three components will be shown in detail.

1.6 Experience and conclusion

We will close the presentation with some thoughts about the development experience working with Web APIs, how things have improved since 2019, and how further improvements to WebAudio could facilitate the use case of game audio.

